

**Threads of Heritage: A Comparative Journey into the Cultures of Georgia
and Kyrgyzstan**

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Abstract

This article critically examines the cultural aspects of Georgian and Kyrgyz cultures, with a specific focus on identifying and exploring their similarities. By considering the influence of historical events, cultural heritages, and social structures, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these two post-Soviet states. Through a unique analytical approach, this study seeks to shed light on the commonalities between these two cultures and enhance our understanding of their shared characteristics. By employing various techniques, this research aims to contribute to the broader field of cultural studies and provide valuable insights into the complexities and nuances of Georgian and Kyrgyz cultures.

Keywords: Kyrgyzstan, Georgia, Cultures, History, Religion, Comparison.

Introduction

Georgia and Kyrgyzstan are two post-Soviet states situated in the regions of the Caucasus and Central Asia. These countries share common characteristics such as mountainous terrain, a significant historical background, and a rich cultural heritage. Georgia shares its borders with Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Turkey, while Kyrgyzstan is bordered by Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and China. The distinct cultural features of these nations have been shaped by their unique climatic conditions and historical influences. To fully understand the similarities and differences between these cultures it is important to explore them in various ways like examining the influence of historical events on their culture, exploring their cultural heritages and diversities, and analyzing the family and social structures presented in the countries.

Historical Background

The historical context of Georgian Culture

The historical origins of Georgia can be traced back to ancient times, encompassing a vast expanse of thousands of years. Remarkably, Georgia is home to some of the oldest European human fossils discovered to date, underscoring its enduring historical significance. It is reasonable to assert that the cultural development of the region has persisted since ancient

times. Many events throughout the course of Georgian history have influenced the culture, traditions, and worldview of the country's population.

The history of Georgia starts in the Stone Age period. On the territory of Dmainisi, scientists found fossils of humans that are around 1.7 million years old and some primitive stone weapons. Those humans are one of the oldest in the whole Eurasian continent. Later, through the stone and bronze ages, many ancient artifacts were found on the territory of Georgia including the weapons and jewelry made out of various metals. As an example, one of the most famous ancient artifacts is the golden figure of a lion that was discovered in a luxurious Korgani tomb. It dates back to the second half of the III millennium B. C. and is one of the outstanding examples of the Early Bronze Age. For that reason, many scientists believe that the region of the South Caucasus is the first place where people started processing the metal. Ancient culture flourished on Georgian land, which has a positive impact on contemporary Georgians' perspectives and is a source of national pride. However, tracing Georgian ethnicity's ancestry is challenging.

Historians and scientists have always been interested in the origins of the Georgian people. There have been many theories about the genesis of this ethnicity. One of the first theories was written by ancient Greek historian and geographer, Herodotus. He said that ancient Georgians are of Egyptian origin. According to him, they must have been descendants of the warriors of the Egyptian king Sesostri, who stayed near the Phazi (Rion) River. Herodotus believed in this because Georgians, like the Egyptians, are dark-skinned and curly-haired, and both practice circumcision, cultivate flax in the same way, and so on. This theory illustrates some parts of the culture of ancient Georgians. Another theory was made but 11th-century Georgian chronicler, Leonti Mroveli, who stated that Georgians have biblical origins, and they migrated from Babylon when the tower was destroyed. Moreover, another theory suggests that Georgian are related to Hittites and Sumerians because there are many similar words in Georgian and their languages. But this only shows that ancient Georgians had close relations with those nations, and they even influenced the modern Georgian language. Finally, scientists agreed that Georgians are an autochthonous nation of the Caucasus. Linguistic analysis of the Georgian language helped them to come to that decision.

The earliest cultures that thrived within the territory of Georgia were the Colchian and Iberian civilizations. Colchis was located in the western part of modern-day Georgia and occupied a big portion of the black seacoast. One of the first mentions of the Colchis is an ancient Greek myth about Argonauts. According to the myth the Greek prince Argos traveled to Colchis and took from there golden Fleece and the princess Medea. Colchians were

renowned for their distinctive techniques of acquiring gold which is well described in the myth. The best representation of the Colchian culture is given by Herodotus. In his works, he presents various aspects of the Colchis like socioeconomic, and geopolitical position. Based on his descriptions and various artifacts that were found on the territory of the Colchis, it seems like the Colchian people had relations with ancient Greek, Persian, Syrian, and Egyptian cultures. They were engaged in active trading and shared various cultural aspects through it. Conversely, the Iberian civilization predominantly occupied the eastern part of present-day Georgia, emerging in the 3rd century BCE. The first and second king of Iberia was Pharnavaz. According to the old Georgian history book "Life of Kartli", he was the one who created the first Georgian Alphabet, which is a huge contribution to Georgian culture. Iberians back then adored the ancient Pantheon of Armazi. Throughout this period, Iberia exerted a profound influence on the sociopolitical landscape of the region. A very important trade route was going through the capital city of Iberia, Mtskheta. Resources from India were moving to the Western world through this route. This also influenced the cultural and economic development of the country. It is noteworthy that Iberia was the second nation in the world to embrace Christianity, which is base of almost the whole of modern Georgian culture. Vestiges of these ancient customs continue to permeate modern Georgian culture (მელიქიძევილი Et al, 2012).

Most of the time throughout history, Georgia was divided into many Kingdoms and was rarely united. Georgia has been a united, independent state only in these years: 975 - 1225, 1329 -1491, 1918-1921, 1990 - present. Various kingdoms like Kartli, Abkhazia, Egrisi, and Imereti emerged on the territory of Georgia which played a significant role in the development of the nation's culture. Those kingdoms were prominent for different aspects of the culture and influenced traditions in numerous ways.

Later in history, Iberia was renamed and called the Kingdom of Kartli. The Kingdom of Kartli was a major center of culture and learning, and it played a significant role in the development of the Georgian language and literature. The Georgian alphabet officially emerged in the 5th century AD. The first literature developed in the 5th century AD. Yakob Khutse's "Tsamebai Tsmindisa Shushanikisi Dedoflisai" of the 5th century is considered the oldest literary work. Other old works are "Peace and Patience of Saint Eustathius of Mtskheteli" 5th century and Iovane Sabanisdze's " Martyrdom of the Holy and Blessed Martyr Christ Habo" which was written in 786-790 years. It is one of the most important symbols of Georgian identity. Often people of Kartli were invaded by Persians, Romans, and later Turk Seljuks. All those invasions left a huge mark on Georgian Culture. Persian architecture can still be found

in Tbilisi. Also, in the Mtskheta, there is an ancient Bridge that was built by Romans during one of the invasions in 65 B.C. Kartli's invaders had a huge influence on the language of Georgian. Many Persian, Turkic, and Arabic words like "Ghalati", "Gandzi", "Suphra" and others are used in the modern Georgian language without even knowing that they are barbarisms (ლორთქიფანიძე et al, 2012).

Similar to Kartli, the descendant of the ancient Colchis was Egrisi. The Egrisian People continued the traditions and lifestyle that were common in Colchis. They were living with trade and shipbuilding. Many coins from the ancient world have been found in the territory of Egrisi. This tells us that Egrisians continued to have close communication with various nations and shared culture with them. People in Egrisi easily adopted Christianity and monks from Egrisi even participated in the First Council of Nicaea. Egrisian people also face various invaders like Romans, Byzantium, and later Turkey.

The Kingdom of Abkhazia holds significant historical importance within the Georgian context. Established in the 8th century AD. Renowned as a prominent hub of trade and commerce, the Kingdom of Abkhazia played a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of Georgian art and architecture, leaving an indelible mark on the cultural heritage of the region. It stood as a vibrant epicenter, fostering the growth of artistic expression and intellectual pursuits. The captivating Abkhazian capital, Sukhumi, thrived as a renowned bastion of learning and culture, attracting and nurturing a myriad of accomplished Georgian scholars and artists who contributed profoundly to the kingdom's rich intellectual tapestry.

The inception of the Kingdom of Imereti in the 15th century AD marked the beginning of an enduring legacy. Renowned as a formidable center of both agricultural prowess and industrial enterprise, this realm played a pivotal role in shaping the development of Georgian music and dance. Its robust agricultural and industrial sectors not only fostered economic prosperity but also nurtured a fertile ground for cultural expression and ingenuity. Kutaisi, the eminent capital of Imereti, emerged as a vibrant nucleus of Georgian culture, attracting and nurturing a cadre of esteemed musicians and dancers who left an indelible imprint on the cultural fabric of the region. The contributions of these and other Georgian kingdoms to shaping Georgian culture are vast and varied. They have helped to shape the Georgian language, literature, art, architecture, music, dance, and social structures. Georgian culture is a vibrant tapestry that is the product of centuries of development.

One of the most influential periods of unified Georgia is the Golden Age. The 11th-13th centuries were the golden age for Georgian culture. During this period, Georgia

experienced a period of political stability and economic prosperity, which allowed art, literature, and architecture to flourish. Georgia's strategic location along the Silk Road has also helped make it a center of cultural exchange. The golden age of Georgian culture was marked by several important achievements in art, literature, and architecture. Many important poets were brought up in Georgia, including Shota Rustaveli, who wrote the epic poem "The Knight in the Panther's Skin". Also, the most impressive churches-monasteries of the region were built in Georgia, among which are the cathedrals of Gelati and Mtskheta (სასთაინი et al, 2012).

Another important influencer on Georgian culture was the Russians. The 19th century saw the beginning of the Russian occupation of Georgia. Russia annexed the Kingdom of Kartli in 1801, and the state became part of the Russian Empire. After that, Russians gradually incorporated other Kingdoms of Georgia into the Empire. Russian influence had a significant impact on Georgian culture, and many aspects of Georgian culture like social structure, and Church were russified. In modern Georgia, the most eye-catching leftover of the Russian influence can be found in language, as many Russian barbarisms are used in Georgian (ბენდიაშვილი et al, 2012).

Furthermore, Russian influence continued to deepen into the Georgian culture as the Soviet Union occupied the country. The Red Army took control of Georgia in 1921, and the country became a republic within the Soviet Union. The Soviet rule had a profound impact on Georgian culture, and many aspects of Georgian culture were suppressed. Patriotic poets and public figures were executed. Georgian church was canceled, and the language was oppressed. Soviets tried to cancel the Georgian language and alphabet but due to the huge protests, they changed their mind. Despite all the hard events that occurred, Georgian culture held up well and kept developing while still maintaining its traits (გაჩეჩილაძე, 2008).

Georgia regained its independence in 1991. Since then, a cultural revival has begun in Georgia and efforts are being made to preserve and popularize Georgian culture. One of the most important areas of cultural revival in Georgia was the revival of arts and crafts. Also, another important aspect of the Georgian cultural revival was the promotion of the Georgian language and literature. Georgian is a unique language and efforts have been renewed to teach it to children. Finally, cultural institutions such as museums, libraries, and theaters have played an important role in the preservation and promotion of Georgian heritage. Cultural revival in Georgia is a positive event and it is important to preserve and promote local culture because Georgian culture is a unique and valuable part of the world's cultural heritage (გაჩეჩილაძე, 2011).

Historical Context of Kyrgyz Culture

The history of the culture in the lands of Kyrgyzstan goes back to ancient times. People settled in the territory of Kyrgyzstan as early as the Lower Paleolithic period. The tools of this age have been found in the Ferghan Valley, near Isik-Khol Lake, and others. The caves, which are decorated with images of animals made with red paint, and other traces of human life belong to the Neolithic Era. Archaeological material confirms that in the Bronze Age, the population here was divided into two groups - farmers and hunters. In the 7th-6th century B.C., fundamental changes took place: iron-made labor and combat weapons spread, class relations arose, nomadic tribes were united in tribal unions, and slave-owning states were formed in the farming regions of the country. In the IV-V centuries, irrigated agriculture and cultivation of new crops began in the southern agricultural regions of Kyrgyzstan. The emergence of cities and the division of labor led to the strengthening of feudal exploitation and tin subjugation of the free population (Здырдог, 1986).

Unlike Georgians, ethnically Kyrgyz people did not always live on the land they inhabit now. According to the Britannica, "History of Kyrgyzstan", the first mentions of Kyrgyz people date back to the 1st century BCE. In that period, they lived in the central parts of Siberia. Kyrgyz people were nomads. At the beginning of the 7th century, the Kyrgyz population followed shamanism, Buddhism, Zoroastrianism, and Christianity, but later Islam started to spread. Their nomadic origin means that they never owned land but rather moved with the seasons. Ancient Kyrgyz culture was deeply connected with nature, especially mountains. According to Noll, D. & Scott, A. (2017), some nomadic traditions like Yurts (Circular homes made from hundreds of pieces of treated wood bound), Salbuurun (a traditional way of hunting with golden eagle), and others, can be observed in modern Kyrgyz societies.

Kyrgyz culture can be perceived as one of the Turkic cultures. Turkic influence can be viewed in various characteristics of Kyrgyz culture like language, names, food, music, clothes, and dances. The most important aspect of Turkic influence is the Kyrgyz language. It is part of the Turkic language group and is related to Kazakh, Uzbek, and Turkish languages. Overall, Turkic people were nomads with similar traditions to Kyrgyz. Due to its nomadic background, similar to other Turkic people, the main source of education for Kyrgyz people was their folklore stories (Golden, P. 1992). In the 10th-12th centuries, the mining of silver and other metals developed, and crafts, trade, and culture were revived in the cities. The conditions were

ripe for the formation of the tribes living in Kyrgyzstan into one people, but the invasion of the Mongols in the first half of the 13th century interrupted this process for a long time.

Additionally, the arousal of the Mongol empire had a huge influence on Kyrgyzstan. Genghis Khan incorporated Kyrgyz people into his empire at the beginning of the 13th century. Mongols occupied Kyrgyz lands and it caused political, economic, and cultural changes. Nomadic herding has become the dominant branch of agriculture in Kyrgyzstan. As a result of the Mongol domination, many nomadic tribes moved here, Eastern Turkestan and part of Tian-Shan were included in the Chagatai Ulus, and Mongol feudal principalities were created. Also, Mongol invasions helped Kyrgyz people to engage in life on the Silk Road. Mongols were famous for their administration talent, and they drastically changed the Kyrgyz style of rule that was based on tribal structure.

The Mongol invasions fostered the growth of ties between East Asia, the Middle East, and Europe through developing connections between different parts of the Silk Road. The Kyrgyz were impacted as well. The Mongols promoted the Silk Road's expansion in importance, which increased commerce, diplomatic relations, religious exchange, and other types of contact between the Kyrgyz and other civilizations.

The Silk Road facilitated the interchange of trade, ideas, and cultural expressions. Kyrgyzstan is situated on the crossroads of the Silk Road, where East Asia and the Middle East are connecting. Similarly, to Georgia, engagement in the life of the Silk Road caused many different cultures like Persian, Arabic, Indian, and Chinese to influence various aspects of Kyrgyz society such as language, art, architecture, and most important, religion.

One of the most major changes that Mongol Invasions brought to Kyrgyz civilization, is Islam. Mongols themselves were adherents of shamanism yet they did not suppress other faiths and permitted conquered nations to have religious freedom. This and the reality that the importance of the Silk Road was fast expanding, encouraged Islamic merchants to disseminate their beliefs. Kyrgyzstan was one of the places they first began to settle. Islam eventually found its place in Kyrgyz society and is now the most practiced religion in the country.

Other than that, the Mongols introduced Kyrgyzstan to advanced technology for farming. To expand settled agriculture in the area, irrigation systems were encouraged. As Kyrgyz Society was nomadic and did not have settled places to live, this innovation brought prosperity to the development and stability of the region.

On the other hand, Mongol rule brought many challenges to the life of the Kyrgyz people. The locals were obligated to always pay taxes and send their men to Mongol military campaigns which damaged the social construct. Moreover, after the death of Genghis Khan,

the great Mongol empire started to fall. The empire was divided into different hordes, which were ruled by the great emperor's descendants. Drastic shifts in the political life of the region caused a lot of instabilities and were tough for Kyrgyz society. In the second half of the 15th century, after the unification of the Kyrgyz tribes, an independent dynasty was formed. The formation of the Kyrgyz people was caused by the liquidation of the feudal lordship of the Mongols (Здырдог, 1986).

Another important external influencer on Kyrgyz culture, was the Russians. Like Georgians, Kyrgyz people were part of the Russian empire at first, and the Soviet Union after. At the end of the 18th century and the beginning of the 19th century, the difficult foreign political situation, unstable domestic situation, and trade interests forced the Kyrgyz to come under the protection of Russia. In the first half of the 19th century, when the Kokand Khanate conquered Kyrgyzstan, contact with Russia ceased. Intensified exploitation on the part of the feudal Khans led to anti-Kokand uprisings (5 great uprisings - 1843-76). In the middle of the 19th century, the conditions for rapprochement with Russia were created. In 1863, Northern Kyrgyzstan voluntarily joined Russia, and in 1876, after the liquidation of the Kokand Khanate, its southern regions. The positive result of the accession of Kyrgyzstan to Russia was the prohibition of slavery, the cessation of feudal civil wars, and the unified resistance of the Kyrgyz and Russian people against tsarism and exploiters (Здырдог, 1986). Also, even though, Russian policy was not aimed to educate locals, they still have a big part in educational development. The presence of Russians made possible of first publication of the Kyrgyz language in the 20th century (Curtis & Library of Congress, 1997).

But Russians brought a lot of struggles to the Kyrgyz people. The Urkun, commonly referred to as the "exodus," is a crucial occasion in Kyrgyz history that happened in 1916. To put down a revolt brought on by unpopular policies, the Tsarist rulers waged a cruel battle against the indigenous people of the Semirechye area in northern Kyrgyzstan. An estimated 100,000 to 200,000 ethnic Kyrgyz were killed as a result of this repression, which is sometimes referred to as the "unknown genocide," while a similar number fled and perished while attempting to escape the Chinese border. Under Tsarist and Soviet authority, the memory and interpretation of the Urkun underwent significant alteration. The Soviet authorities intentionally manipulated and suppressed key parts of the event to fit their ideological framework (Chokobaeva, 2015).

In the 20th century, like Georgia, Kyrgyzstan became part of the Soviet Union. Being part of such a big empire had a significant influence on Kyrgyz culture as well. The author

analyzed the influence of some Soviet policies, like collectivization, industrialization, and assimilation efforts on Kyrgyz culture.

The Soviets implemented collectivism, which is a collectivistic type of farming. This type of farm goes against Kyrgyz nomadic traditions. The traditional pastoral practices were destroyed as the Soviets forced herders to give up on their livestock and join the collectivist farm. This caused a shift in Kyrgyz society from nomadic traditions and eventually, many customs related to animal husbandry were lost.

The Soviet Union focused on the development of heavy industries in Kyrgyzstan. As factories were built in the big cities people started to migrate and the urbanization process began. This encouraged a significant change in traditional rural communities and resulted in a shift in social structures, lifestyles, and economic activities.

During the Soviet era, initiatives to assimilate cultures were also prevalent. The Russian language and culture were promoted as the dominating framework in an effort by the Soviet authorities to forge a single, cohesive Soviet identity. Russian was widely utilized in government, education, and the media, and Russian language instruction became required. The Kyrgyz language was significantly impacted by this, both in terms of usage and status, especially among the educated urban population.

The Soviet leadership also put programs in place to change long-standing cultural norms and advance Soviet ideals. Folklore, music, and dance, which are traditional cultural manifestations, were frequently reinterpreted through a Soviet lens, stressing socialist themes and spreading Soviet ideas. If they were thought to be inconsistent with Soviet ideology, traditional customs, and behaviors were likewise discouraged or prohibited. It is important to note that while changing Kyrgyz culture due to the policies, the Soviets also tried to preserve some customs. The shifts in Kyrgyz culture varied from region to region (Bektursunov, 2022).

In 1991, when the Soviet Union collapsed, Kyrgyzstan and other Soviet republics gained their independence. After a long time in the Russian Empire and the Soviet Union, many traditions were lost. Similar to Georgia, in the times of independence, the process of revival of Kyrgyz culture and traditions began. Efforts were made to reclaim and preserve Kyrgyz's cultural heritage, leading to the revitalization of traditional arts, music, dance, and language.

One of the important aspects of Kyrgyz culture was craftsmanship. According to Curtis & Library of Congress, (1997), after regaining independence, organizations and individuals were selflessly working on the resurgence of traditional practices like felt-making, weaving, and pottery. These efforts were resultative, and they did not only renew the culture but also helped artists to embrace their potential and develop economically.

There has been a resurgence of traditional Kyrgyz music, which includes instruments like the Komuz and the Ky-Kayak, in addition to song and dance. At cultural events, festivals, and other occasions both domestically and internationally, traditional bands, folk musicians, and folk-dance groups have begun to perform. Traditional Kyrgyz dances are resurfacing, with their vibrant costumes and intricate choreography. Dance ensembles perform while maintaining their cultural legacy (Levin, et al. 2016).

Language revival is one of the most important aspects of the cultural renaissance. According to Korth (2015), there are also cultural institutions and language schools in addition to language immersion programs. Language is increasingly used in media and education in addition to daily life. This is essential to ensure that the language is transmitted to future generations. Cultural revival focused on similar aspects of Kyrgyz and Georgian cultures.

It is important to put efforts into saving and restoring Kyrgyz culture as it is a unique collaboration of nomadic, Islamic, and Central Asian traditions.

Cultural Overlook

Examining multiple aspects of a culture, such as religion, music, art, and other characteristics is crucial if one wants to fully comprehend the cultures of Georgia and Kyrgyzstan.

The religious landscape in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan

The religious landscapes presented in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan represent the diversity of spiritual traditions of these countries. Since it became the official religion of Georgia in the fourth century, Christianity has had a significant impact on the country's culture. The Georgian Orthodox Church has been an important part of society and has had an impact on a wide range of facets of Georgian culture, including art, architecture, literature, and religious rituals. One of the oldest Christian churches in the world, the Georgian Orthodox Church has contributed significantly to the growth of Georgian culture. According to Mikaberidze (2007), about 88 percent of the Georgian population is Christian, and 83 percent belongs to the Georgian Orthodox Church. The church has been an important promoter of the arts, and Georgia is home to several beautiful monasteries consequently. The church has contributed to the growth of Georgian writing, and many of the nation's most well-known authors have been worshipers. Besides the Georgian Orthodox Church, there are also representatives of other religions such as the Armenian Apostolic Church, Muslims, Jews, Catholics, and so on. This diversity of

religions in the country represents the tolerance and freedom that are part of Georgian culture. The best example of these qualities is the fact that Tbilisi is one of the rare places in the world where a church, mosque, and synagogue were built side by side.

Unlike Georgia, the predominant religion in Kyrgyzstan is Islam. Islam has been present in Central Asia for over 1300 years (Engvall, 2020). The Kyrgyz people have been influenced by various branches of Islam such as the Sunni and Sufi traditions. In Kyrgyzstan today, mosques can be found throughout the whole country. Islam is part of the daily life of the Kyrgyz and influences their customs, traditions, and behavior. Despite Georgia and Kyrgyzstan being predominantly Muslim and Christian countries, they are both religiously diverse places. In Kyrgyzstan, one can encounter various religions such as the Russian Orthodox Church, Catholic, and Protestant denominations, as well as followers of indigenous spiritual practices and beliefs, in addition to Islam. This religious diversity enriches Kyrgyzstan's cultural landscape and fosters interfaith communication and respect amongst various religious groups.

Language diversity in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan

The diversity of languages is evidence of the different backgrounds and historical influences that have affected both Georgia and Kyrgyzstan. It symbolizes the coexistence of several ethnic groups and their respective languages and contributes to the countries' rich cultural tapestry.

Georgia is a linguistically diverse country. The official language in Georgia is Georgian, which belongs to the Kartvelian language group. The Kartvelian language group is unique and unrelated to any other language group in the world. The four languages in the group are Georgian, Megrelian, Svan, and Laz. Georgian is the most popular of these languages and is spoken throughout the whole country. The Georgian language has its unique alphabet, which is one of the 14 writing systems in the world. The Georgian language has had three alphabets throughout history, but today only one is used in daily life. Svan is spoken in the northwestern part of Georgia. Megrelian speakers border the Svan people and live on the coast of the Black Sea, south of Abkhazia. The Laz language is closely related to Megrelian, and Laz speakers live mainly in the historic Georgian areas that are now part of Turkey. Apart from the Kartvelian languages, you can also encounter Armenian, Azerbaijani, Ossetian, Abkhazian, and Chechen speakers in Georgia. Due to Russian and Soviet influence, many Georgians of the older generation can speak the Russian language. This diversity of languages reflects the multiculturalism and tolerance of the country (Gabunia, 2014).

Similar to Georgia, Kyrgyzstan is rich with various languages that are used in the territory of the country. The official language of Kyrgyzstan is Kyrgyz language. The Kyrgyz language belongs to the Western (Kipchak) group of Turkic languages. It is spread mainly in Kyrgyzstan, as well as in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, China (Xinjiang), and Afghanistan. It has 2 dialects: northern and southern. The Kyrgyz language is characterized by a sharp differentiation of voiceless and voiced phonemes and reduced suffixes. The language was influenced by the languages of the Kipchak group. There are many borrowed words from Mongolian, Russian, as well as Arabic-Persian lexical elements. At first, Arabic writing was used in Kyrgyzstan, then Latin. Since 1940, Kyrgyz's script is based on Russian graphics. As Georgia and Kyrgyzstan were both under Russian influence for a long time, Russian is also spoken among the Kyrgyz people. It also holds significant status as a widely spoken language and serves as a lingua franca for interethnic communication, business, and education. Furthermore, languages like Uzbek, Kazakh, Tajik, and Dungan are also spoken in the country. Like in Georgia, linguistic diversity shows the cross-cultural location of Kyrgyzstan which influenced such a situation in the country (აბაშიძე, 1986).

Traditional arts and crafts in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan

Traditional arts and crafts are of great importance in both countries. They serve as an expression of regional identity, the promotion of artistic talent, and the preservation of cultural history. By often incorporating symbolic components, motifs, and patterns that symbolize their traditions and beliefs, handicrafts frequently reflect the historical and cultural narratives of communities. As both residents and visitors appreciate these products, they also support the economy and livelihood of the artists. A sense of pride, cultural continuity, and information sharing is also fostered through the preservation and promotion of traditional arts and crafts. This ensures that these rich artistic traditions are preserved for future generations.

Georgians engage in traditional crafts such as carpet weaving, metalworking, pottery, and others. Georgian carpets, also known as "Kilim" or "Palas," are known for their intricate patterns and vivid colors that depict local culture and customs. Georgian wood crafts are known for their intricately carved musical instruments, furniture, and accessories. Handmade clay vessels with ornamental motifs and geometric designs are known as pottery. In metalworking, jewelry, belt buckles, daggers, and other decorative items are made using various metalworking techniques. Icon painting, which originated in Orthodox Christianity, preserves religious and cultural history through the production of sacred icons (Dvalishvili, et al, 2012).

Similarly, Kyrgyzstan's traditional arts and crafts are an important part of the nation's cultural heritage. One such craft is felt-making, which is also called "Alakiyiz" or "Shyrdak." Skilled craftspeople use ancient techniques to create intricate patterns and motifs on felt. Textile weaving and embroidery are also highly regarded creative traditions in Kyrgyzstan, particularly among women who produce beautiful designs on fabrics and clothing. Carpet weaving is also a very popular type of arts and crafts in Kyrgyzstan. The country is also renowned for its masterfully crafted silver jewelry and ornamental objects that feature filigree work. Moreover, talented craftspeople create traditional musical instruments such as the two-stringed Kyl Kiyak and the three-stringed Komuz (Sartbekova, et al, 2019).

Music and dance traditions of Georgia and Kyrgyzstan

In both Georgia and Kyrgyzstan, music and dance traditions have special significance for society. They are an expression of cultural identity and foster a sense of community and belonging. Stories, morals, and traditions are passed on through music and dance, linking past and present. In addition, this part of culture plays a major role in the tourism industry, as people are excited to see such a unique expression of culture as dances and music in Kyrgyzstan and Georgia. Furthermore, dance and music traditions have a significant role in inspiring new generations to embrace the culture of their home countries.

In Georgia, there is a rich tradition of music and dance that is an integral part of festivals, ceremonies, and social gatherings. One of the most significant forms of music is Georgian polyphonic singing, which has been recognized by UNESCO as an Intangible Cultural Heritage (Tsitsishvili, 2009). This style of singing is characterized by multipart harmonies and emotive vocal performances that often depict romantic, natural, and historical themes. Traditional Georgian instruments, such as the Panduri (a three-stringed lute) and doli (a drum), provide rhythmic accompaniment to the songs. Georgian dance is also renowned for its lively and dynamic movements that demonstrate the dancers' skill and grace. The intricate footwork, expressive gestures, and colorful costumes of traditional dances are a reflection of Georgian culture and the diversity of local dance genres.

Kyrgyzstan's rich cultural past and nomadic culture of Kyrgyzstan are closely intertwined with the country's traditional dances and music. Georgian and Kyrgyz music and dance traditions are not alike. Until 1917, Kyrgyz music existed only in the form of folklore. Vocal music was represented by genre-varied monophonic singing. The genre of cue (a large programmatic piece) is widespread in instrumental music. Folk instruments are Komuz, Kil Kiyak, Zhigach Ooz Komuz, Temir Komuz, Choor, Surnai, Kerney, and Dobulbas or Dool

(სბაშიძე, 1986). Music is frequently used to narrate epic tales and stories about historical figures and great deeds. The traditional Kyrgyz dance "Kara Jorgo" is distinguished by its lovely gestures, deft footwork, and swirling movements. The dances are often performed in colorful traditional clothing with intricate embroidery and patterns. In addition to being enjoyable, Kyrgyz music and dance traditions are not only entertaining, but also promote community cohesion, preserve cultural identity, and transmit traditions from one generation to the next (Levin et al., 2016).

Traditional clothing in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan

The distinctive cultural identities and historical influences of each nation are reflected in the traditional clothes of Georgia and Kyrgyzstan. Traditional attire has become essential for cultural events, festivals, and celebrations. Even though, in modern times traditional cloth in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan are only used to showcase their culture and help people connect with their ancestral traditions, the cloth used to be very useful in everyday life. Traditional clothes are practical for local climates and needs.

In Georgia, the cultural diversity that is present in the country can be viewed by looking at traditional cloth as well. In different regions of Georgia, people have their unique pieces of clothing. In every region traditional hats also differ. The most popular traditional cloth in Georgia is Chokha. It is a coat-like dress that is worn by men and is decorated with embroidery, metalwork, and ornate belts. The most iconic hat for the nation is the Papakha, which is made out of wool (Patsaia, 2018).

Traditional dress in Kyrgyzstan recalls the Kyrgyz people's nomadic past. The Beshik Kurt, a long, robe-like coat made of wool or felt, is a common garment worn by males. The Koylek, a garment for women that often features elaborate embroidery and is composed of multicolored silk fabric, is a part of traditional apparel for women. The most recognizable piece of apparel in Kyrgyzstan is arguably the Kalpak, a tall hat made of white felt. The Kalpak serves as an identifier for the Kyrgyz people among other ethnic groups. Sometimes a delicately embroidered Kalpak and felt coat would be given to honored guests. An essential part of Kyrgyz traditional clothing is the Elechek, a headpiece embellished with feathers and coins for decoration. Men and women both wear the traditional belt known as the Koshma, which has complex decorations and is frequently made of leather or cloth. According to the article by CGTN (2019).

Georgian and Kyrgyz cuisine

Both Georgia and Kyrgyzstan offer very rich food traditions with unique flavors and cooking techniques that reflect the countries' diverse and amusing cultures. In both of these states, people use spices, herbs, and various flavor combinations to make extremely unique and tasty dishes. Food culture in those regions not only showcases the brilliance of local gastronomic traditions but also reflects on both countries' hospitality and communal dining experiences.

Georgia is famous for its astonishing cuisine that shocks visitors from all over the globe. Due to the numerous invaders and visitors, Georgia unavoidably adopted several foreign customs, including some culinary influences. Georgian cuisine has flavors that are evocative of both Mediterranean and Middle Eastern cuisine as a consequence of the complex blending of culinary concepts that merchants and travelers alike brought with them on trade routes. However, the Georgians did not accept all the culinary customs that were introduced to them, and as a result, Georgian cuisine continues to be unique, especially considering the significant use of walnuts. Certain borrowed techniques are immediately recognized. The pilafs of southeast Georgia are similar to those of neighboring Iran, and the meats simmered with fruit resemble different types of Persian Khoresh (stew), though Georgians prefer to stew meat with sour plums or pomegranates rather than sweeter fruits like quince or prunes to produce the tart flavor. The famous Georgian khinkali—the filled, boiling dumplings of the upland regions—showcase the Central Asian Turks' gastronomic impact. The stuffed vegetable Tolmas in western Georgia along the Black Sea coast resemble the numerous dolmas of Turkey. But Georgians have never acquired a taste for the intricate oriental desserts made in Turkish, Persian, or Armenian kitchens; instead, they tend to stick to desserts made mostly of fresh fruit and nuts (Goldstein, 2007).

Kyrgyz food reflects the nomadic lifestyle that the nation used to have throughout history. Nomads had to always move from one place to another therefore, their food was high in calories and very nutritious. Some of Kyrgyz's food like "Sumolok" showcase the national celebrations as they are served only on special occasions. One of the most popular Kyrgyz dishes is Beshbarmak, which is a lamb with some noodles and onion sauce served and made with special traditional techniques. Manty is another popular product in Kyrgyzstan. It is a dumpling filled with meat and prepared on steam. Manty is somewhat similar to Georgian Khinkali. Additionally, fermented dairy items like Kymyz (fermented mare's milk) and Airan

(a sort of yogurt beverage) are used in Kyrgyz cuisine. In addition, there are many different substantial soups, grilled meats, and regional breads in Kyrgyz cuisine. According to an Article by Central Asia Guide, *Traditional Kyrgyz Food*, (2021).

Family and Social Structure

To completely understand the culture of the country it is extremely important to not only check the historical or cultural heritage but also examine the social construct that is accepted in certain societies. Learning the social structure will help to understand how average citizens of some nations think, and what kind of mindset they have. Both Georgia and Kyrgyzstan are traditional countries with conservative norms and morals. Religious influence also plays a role in the norms of the country. Kyrgyzstan is mostly a Muslim country and Islam is famous for keeping their traditions alive. On the other hand, Georgia is mainly a Christian country, but the Orthodox Church is one of the most old-fashioned branches of Christianity; so, religious norms and morals are very popular in the nation's society. For the best understanding of the family and social structure in Georgia and Kyrgyzstan, Hofstede's five cultural dimensions would help the best.

Geert Hofstede was a Dutch scholar whose work on cultural dimensions is among the most widely cited for understanding cultural variation. His research program ran from 1967 to 1973 and explored the behaviors of over 100,000 people in work settings. Despite the large number of participants, the narrow focus on the workplace has led to questions about generalizing the research to other populations and places. Still, this work represents one of the most comprehensive attempts to compare aspects of culture. Hofstede identified five cultural dimensions. While initially there were only four, he later added a fifth to address Eastern and Western differences. The dimensions include Individualism/Collectivism, Power Distance, Masculinity/Femininity, Uncertainty Avoidance, and Long-term/Short-term Orientation.

Of Hofstede's five dimensions, Individualism/Collectivism is his most cited by far. It is a measure of the extent to which people in a culture are expected to "do their own thing" (individualism), or act as part of a group (collectivism). The dimension of individualism and collectivism exerts a powerful hold on how members of a culture see themselves in relation to others, how they develop self-esteem, and how they choose to interact with members of their society. It is more usual for Asian countries to be more on the scale of the collectivistic culture. Hofstede-insights.com provides a tool to see approximate measures of each country on various scales of Hofstede's dimensions. According to that scale, Georgia scores 41 on the scale of

individualism, while Kyrgyzstan – 30. Both of those scores are lower than average, which tells that in those countries people tend to associate themselves with some groups. Kyrgyzstan has a lower score; accordingly, Kyrgyz people are more collectivistic than Georgians. It is very common in these cultures to perceive yourself as a part of religion, or family and it is not surprising that both of those states have low scores on the scale of individualism.

Power distance is the extent to which all groups in society assume that power is distributed unequally. It is important to note that the system is based on the perspective of those in the "one down" position. This implies that systems of power work only when the "haves" and the "have-nots" both somehow endorse the inequality. Some societies tend more toward egalitarianism. Israel, for example, is identified as a very low power distance culture. It is a country characterized by lots of active political debate and many varied political parties. Elections are not winner-take; rather, proportional representation allows smaller constituencies to share power. Of course, the challenge within the Israeli system, often identified as the only democracy in the Middle East, is to find a way of extending the sense of inclusion, respect, and participation to Palestinians living in that part of the world. In some societies, power can be distributed according to Gender, race, or other characteristics. Power Distance can be seen in the language that we use. For example, cultures with high power Distance use more respectful form of language that praises others. On the scale, Georgia scores 65 and Kyrgyzstan – 70. These scores are high, and the countries are similar in this cultural dimension as well.

Hofstede's masculinity/femininity dimension refers to the distribution and distinction of roles between the genders. In high-masculinity societies, gender roles are clearly distinguished, and qualities like competitiveness and assertiveness are valued. In what are identified as feminine cultures, male and female roles converge and qualities like caring and cooperation are prized. On this scale, Georgia scores 55 and Kyrgyzstan – 43. It is unexpected but none of these countries turned out to be very masculine. Georgia scored a bit higher than average while Kyrgyzstan's score is low. This tells us that in these societies, features like assertiveness and competitiveness are strongly praised.

Uncertainty Avoidance. The dimension of uncertainty avoidance refers to the degree of comfort with ambiguity. Countries high on uncertainty avoidance tend to focus on identifying the best way and establishing clearly defined rules. In low-uncertain settings, a wider range of behaviors are acceptable, and tolerance for variation is more common. This scale showed that Georgians and Kyrgyz people do not like to feel ambiguity. They are more comfortable having everything certain in detail. Both of the above-mentioned countries score very high on uncertainty avoidance with a result of 85 for Georgia and 93 for Kyrgyzstan. It is quite

unexpected because Georgian are characterized by unpunctuality. This is one of the main attributes of a culture with low uncertainty avoidance.

Hofstede added Confucian dynamism (also referred to as long-term short-term orientation) as a fifth and final dimension because one critique of his work was that it did not adequately reflect Eastern Asian values and perspectives. A long-term, Eastern orientation emphasizes perseverance, thrift, and humility. This is in contrast to a focus on the immediate gratification and relative excesses of short-term cultures. The impact of Confucianism (Hofstede referred to Confucian philosophy in laying out the dimension that distinguishes short-term and long-term perspectives. Born in China around 551 BCE, Confucius came along at a time of political and social turmoil when individualism threatened their culture. As an antidote to a corrupt every-man-for-himself system, social harmony and appropriate relationship roles were key elements in Confucian philosophy, with a focus on self-discipline being central. The influence of Confucianism spread from China throughout East Asia.) shapes the orientation and is credited by some for driving the economic emergence of certain Asian cultures including China, Japan, and South Korea. This dimension can be seen in people's attitudes towards expenses. Ones who are more focused on savings and live by looking at the future rather than having pleasure today are Long-term orientation cultures. Georgia's and Kyrgyzstan's outcomes are 38 and 53. In this dimension, we can see the difference between these cultures. While Kyrgyz people tend to be concentrated more on the future, Georgians like to enjoy what they have now (Remland et al, 2015).

Overall, the most relevant way to compare and study Georgian and Kyrgyz Family and Social structures is to do it according to Hofstede's five cultural dimensions. The scales showed that Georgian and Kyrgyz mindsets and perceptions are very similar. Out of five, only on the scale of Long-term orientation, they had noticeably different scores. All above mentioned indicate that similar geographical location, geopolitical importance, and some historical events former in these cultures, analogous worldviews, and social construct

Conclusion

The paper examined Georgian and Kyrgyz cultures with various techniques. They are fascinating countries with astonishing cultures. At first, the paper viewed the historical events that influenced states' traditions. Georgia and Kyrgyzstan both have very important geopolitical locations which resulted in some similar events that occurred throughout their history. Secondly, the paper overlooked the cultures. It is important to note that both countries have

very diverse and rich cultures. Diversity is the main similarity between the cultures of Georgia and Kyrgyzstan. Finally, for a better understanding of the lifestyle in those countries, the author decided to examine both cultures from the perspective of Hofstede's five cultural dimensions. As a result, Kyrgyz and Georgian social structures turned out to be very similar with some minor differences. Despite constant pressure from other cultures, Kyrgyz and Georgian people managed to keep their ancient traditions alive while creating unique mixture cultures. It is amazing to realize that two nations that had almost no interaction throughout history and no relevance with each other can have so many similarities in their cultures.

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